

Overview on antibiotic resistance

By

Hosea danjuma

Matric number: hsl/21/0789

Being a seminar presented to the department of science laboratory technology

In partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of higher national diploma (HND) in science laboratory technology, waziri umaru federal polytechnic, birnin kebbi, kebbi state.

June, 2023

Abstract

Resistance to antibiotic has become a major source of morbidity and mortality worldwide. When antibiotics were first introduced in the 1900's, it was thought that we had won the war against microorganisms. It was soon discovered however, that the microorganisms were capable of developing resistance to any of the drugs that were used. Apparently most pathogenic microorganisms have the capability of developing resistance to at least some antimicrobial agents. The main mechanisms of resistance are: limiting uptake of a drug, modification of a drug target, inactivation of a drug, and active efflux of a drug. These mechanisms may be native to the microorganisms, or acquired from other microorganisms. Understanding more about these mechanisms should hopefully lead to better treatment options for infective diseases, and development of antimicrobial drugs that can withstand the microorganisms attempts to become resistant.

1.0 Introduction

With the discovery of antibiotics, the healthcare community thought that the battle with infectious diseases was won. However, now that so many bacteria have become resistant to multiple antimicrobial agents, the war has seemingly escalated in favor of the bacteria. Infectious diseases are currently a significant cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide. An assessment of these diseases by the World Health Organization (WHO 2014) found that lower respiratory infection, diarrheal diseases, HIV/AIDS, and malaria are in the top ten contributors to morbidity and mortality. The advent of antimicrobial resistance has added significantly to the impact of infectious diseases, in number of infections, as well as added healthcare costs. Even though we have a very large number of antimicrobial agents from which to choose for potential infection therapy, there is documented antimicrobial resistance to all of these, and this resistance occurs shortly after a new drug is okayed for use. These concerns prompted the WHO to launch a Global Action Plan on antimicrobial resistance in 2015 (who 2015).

Antibiotic resistance is ancient and it is the expected result of the interaction of many organisms with their environment. Most antimicrobial compounds are naturally-produced molecules, and, as such, co-resident bacteria have evolved mechanisms to overcome their action in order to survive. Thus, these organisms are often considered to be “intrinsically” resistant to one or more antimicrobials. However, when discussing the antimicrobial resistance conundrum, bacteria harboring intrinsic determinants of resistance are not the main focus of the problem. Rather, in clinical settings, we are typically referring to the expression of “acquired resistance” in a bacterial population that was originally susceptible to the antimicrobial compound. As it will be discussed later in this work, the development of acquired resistance can be the result of mutations in chromosomal genes or due to the acquisition of external genetic determinants of resistance, likely obtained from intrinsically resistant organisms present in the environment (Coculescu 2009).

Antimicrobial agents can be divided into groups based on the mechanism of antimicrobial activity. The main groups are: agents that inhibit cell wall synthesis, depolarize the cell membrane, inhibit protein synthesis, inhibit nuclei acid synthesis, and inhibit metabolic pathways in bacteria. . It would seem that with such a wide range of mechanisms we would have better control over the organisms. Unfortunately, improper stewardship of antimicrobial agents has helped lead to the tremendous resistance issue that we now face. Factors that have contributed to the growing resistance problem include: increased consumption of antimicrobial drugs, both by humans and animals; and improper prescribing of antimicrobial therapy. Overuse of many common antimicrobials agents by physicians may occur because the choice of drug is based on a combination of low cost and low toxicity. There may also be improper prescribing of antimicrobials drugs, such as the initial prescription of a broad-spectrum drug that is unnecessary, or ultimately found to be ineffective for the organism(s) causing the infection. The danger is that excessive use of antibiotics in humans leads to emergence of resistant organisms. In addition, prior use of antimicrobial drugs puts a patient at risk for infection with a drug resistant organism, and those patients with the highest exposure to antimicrobials are

most often those who are infected with resistant bacteria (CDC 2012).

Exposure of a pathogen to an antimicrobial compound can select for chromosomal mutations conferring resistance, which can be transferred vertically to subsequent microbial generations and eventually become predominant in a microbial population that is repeatedly exposed to the antimicrobial. Alternatively, many genes responsible for drug resistance are found on plasmids or in transposons that can be transferred easily between microbes through horizontal gene transfer. Transposons also have the ability to move resistance genes between plasmids and chromosomes to further promote the spread of resistance (CDC 2012).

1.1 antibiotic

An antibiotic can be defined as the substance produced by microorganism or a similar substance (produced either wholly or partially by chemical synthesis) which kill or inhibit the growth of other microorganisms already established in the tissue.

It is also defined as low molecular weight organic compound produced by microorganism that inhibit or kill other microorganisms.

It can be deduced that antibiotic can be categorized into three (3);

- i. Natural or proper antibiotic
- ii. synthetic antibiotic
- iii. Semi-synthetic antibiotic (musliu 2023).

1.2 Resistance

A literal/biological definition of resistance is the capacity of bacteria to withstand the effects of a harmful chemical agent.

Bacterial resistance is the capacity of bacteria to withstand the effects of antibiotics or biocides that are intended to kill or control them.

The term "multiple resistance" (MR) or "multi-resistance" is used when a bacterial strain is resistant to several different antimicrobials or antimicrobial classes. For instance, multi-drug resistant tuberculosis is simultaneously resistant to a number of antibiotics belonging to different chemical classes.

"Cross-resistant" bacteria are those that have developed survival methods that are effective against different types of antimicrobial molecules with similar mechanism(s) of action.

Bacteria can transfer bits of genetic material to other bacteria, and when genetic information coding for several unrelated resistance mechanisms is transferred in a single event and expressed in the new bacterial host it is referred to as “co-resistance” (Keren et al.,2004).

1.3 Antibiotic resistance

Antibiotic Resistance occurs when bacteria change over time and no longer respond to medicines making infections harder to treat and increasing the risk of disease spread, severe illness and death (Macedo-Viñas et al., 2013).

2.0 Mechanisms for Drug Resistance

There are several common mechanisms for drug resistance, which are summarized in the Figure below. These mechanisms include;

1. enzymatic modification of the drug
2. modification of the antimicrobial target
3. prevention of drug penetration or accumulation (Martinez 2014).

1. Drug Modification or Inactivation

Resistance genes may code for enzymes that chemically modify an antimicrobial, thereby inactivating it, or destroy an antimicrobial through hydrolysis. Resistance to many types of antimicrobials occurs through this mechanism. For example, aminoglycoside resistance can occur through enzymatic transfer of chemical groups to the drug molecule, impairing the binding of the drug to its bacterial target. For β -lactams, bacterial resistance can involve the enzymatic hydrolysis of the β -lactam bond within the β -lactam ring of the drug molecule. Once the β -lactam bond is broken, the drug loses its antibacterial activity. This mechanism of resistance is mediated by β -lactamases, which are the most common mechanism of β -lactam resistance. Inactivation of rifampin commonly occurs through glycosylation, phosphorylation, or adenosine diphosphate (ADP) ribosylation, and resistance to macrolides and lincosamides can also occur due to enzymatic inactivation of the drug or modification (Martinez 2014).

2. Prevention of Cellular Uptake or Efflux

Microbes may develop resistance mechanisms that involve inhibiting the accumulation of an antimicrobial drug, which then prevents the drug from reaching its cellular target. This strategy is common among gram-negative pathogens and can involve changes in outer membrane lipid composition, porin channel selectivity, and/or porin channel concentrations. For example, a common mechanism of carbapenem resistance among *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is to decrease the amount of its OprD porin, which is the primary portal of entry for carbapenems through the outer membrane of this pathogen. Additionally, many gram-positive and gram-negative pathogenic bacteria produce efflux pumps that actively transport an antimicrobial drug out of the cell and prevent the accumulation of drug to a level that would be antibacterial. For example, resistance to β -lactams, tetracyclines, and fluoroquinolones commonly occurs through active efflux out of the cell, and it is rather common for a single efflux pump to have the ability to translocate multiple types of antimicrobials (Martinez 2014).

3. Target Modification

Because antimicrobial drugs have very specific targets, structural changes to those targets can prevent drug binding, rendering the drug ineffective. Through spontaneous mutations in the genes encoding antibacterial drug targets, bacteria have an evolutionary advantage that allows them to develop resistance to drugs. This mechanism of resistance development is quite common. Genetic changes impacting the active site of penicillin-binding proteins (PBPs) can inhibit the binding of β -lactam drugs and provide resistance to multiple drugs within this class. This mechanism is very common among strains of *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, which alter their

own PBPs through genetic mechanisms. In contrast, strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* develop resistance to methicillin (MRSA) through the acquisition of a new low-affinity PBP, rather than structurally alter their existing PBPs. Not only does this new low-affinity PBP provide resistance to methicillin but it provides resistance to virtually all β -lactam drugs, with the exception of the newer fifth-generation cephalosporins designed specifically to kill MRSA. Other examples of this resistance strategy include alterations in ribosome subunits, providing resistance to macrolides, tetracyclines, and aminoglycosides; lipopolysaccharide (LPS) structure, providing resistance to polymyxins; RNA polymerase, providing resistance to rifampin; DNA gyrase, providing resistance to fluoroquinolones; metabolic enzymes, providing resistance to sulfa drugs, sulfones, and trimethoprim; and peptidoglycan subunit peptide chains, providing resistance to glycopeptides.

(Martinez 2014).

2.1 Causes of antibiotic resistance'

Antibiotic resistance happens when bacteria change and become resistant to the antibiotics used to treat the infections they cause.

- i. Over-prescribing of antibiotics
- ii. Patients not finishing their treatment
- iii. Over-use of antibiotics in livestock and fish farming
- iv. Poor infection control in hospitals and clinics
- v. Lack of hygiene and poor sanitation
- vi. Lack of new antibiotics being developed (Sandiumenge et al., 2006).

2.2 Prevention and control

Antibiotic resistance is accelerated by the misuse and overuse of antibiotics, as well as poor infection prevention and control. Steps can be taken at all levels of society to reduce the impact and limit the spread of resistance (WHO 2014).

A. Individuals

To prevent and control the spread of antibiotic resistance, individuals can:

- i. Only use antibiotics when prescribed by a certified health professional.
- ii. Never demand antibiotics if your health worker says you don't need them.

- iii. Always follow your health worker's advice when using antibiotics.
- iv. Never share or use leftover antibiotics.
- v. Prevent infections by regularly washing hands, preparing food hygienically, avoiding close contact with sick people, practising safer sex, and keeping vaccinations up to date.
- vi. Prepare food hygienically, following the WHO Five Keys to Safer Food (keep clean, separate raw and cooked, cook thoroughly, keep food at safe temperatures, use safe water and raw materials) and choose foods that have been produced without the use of antibiotics for growth promotion or disease prevention in healthy animals (Tacconelli et al., 2009).

B. Policy makers

To prevent and control the spread of antibiotic resistance, policy makers can:

- i. Ensure a robust national action plan to tackle antibiotic resistance is in place.
- ii. Improve surveillance of antibiotic-resistant infections.
- iii. Strengthen policies, programmes, and implementation of infection prevention and control measures.
- iv. Regulate and promote the appropriate use and disposal of quality medicines.
- v. Make information available on the impact of antibiotic resistance (Tacconelli et al., 2009).

C. Health professionals

To prevent and control the spread of antibiotic resistance, health professionals can:

- i. Prevent infections by ensuring your hands, instruments, and environment are clean.
- ii. Only prescribe and dispense antibiotics when they are needed, according to current guidelines.
- iii. Report antibiotic-resistant infections to surveillance teams.
- iv. Talk to your patients about how to take antibiotics correctly, antibiotic resistance and the dangers of misuse.
- v. Talk to your patients about preventing infections (for example, vaccination, hand washing, safer sex, and covering nose and mouth when sneezing).
- vi. Invest in research and development of new antibiotics, vaccines, diagnostics and other tools (WHO 2014).

2.3 Conclusion

The relentless rise in antibiotic resistance is a major public health concern, which will need to be acted upon now. We might not be able to stop antibiotic resistance or, in many cases, reverse the trend to ever-increasing resistance, but we certainly need to contain the speed to which this is happening. No single action or initiative by a single country would be able to achieve this. It requires participation and support from all levels; political, medical, veterinary, agricultural, environmental, academic, industry and the general public. By creating awareness, maintaining proper hygiene, avoiding self medication, research and development of new antibiotics, vaccines, diagnostics and other tools.

However, it remains to be seen if activities can be sufficiently coordinated worldwide to effect a change in the situation.

References

1. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) Antibiotic resistance threats in the United States, 2013. U.S: Department of Health and Human Services; 2013. p. CS239559-B. [Google Scholar]
2. Coculescu BI. Antimicrobial resistance induced by genetic changes. *J Med Life*. 2009;2:114–123. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
3. Conly J, Johnston B. Where are all the new antibiotics? The new antibiotic paradox. *Can J Infect Dis Med Microbiol* 2005;16:159–60.
3. Macedo-Viñas M, De Angelis G, Rohner P, et al. Burden of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* infections at a Swiss University hospital: excess length of stay and costs. *J Hosp Infect*. 2013;84:132–137. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
4. Martinez JL. General principles of antibiotic resistance in bacteria. *Drug Discov Today*. 2014;11:33–39. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
5. Musliu, Femi. Pharmaceutical industry lecture note. 2023.
6. Sandiumenge A, Diaz E, Rodriguez A, et al. Impact of diversity of antibiotic use on the development of antimicrobial resistance. *J Antimicrob Chemoth*. 2006;57:1197–1204. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
7. Tacconelli E. Antimicrobial use: risk driver of multidrug resistant microorganisms in healthcare settings. *Curr Opin Infect Dis*. 2009;22:352–358. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
8. World Health Organization. World Health Statistics 2014. 2014.
9. World Health Organization. Global action plan on antimicrobial resistance. 2015.